

The kinetic parameters αn_α and k_{th}^0 for the electrode reaction were calculated using the Koutecky method (Table 1). The diffusion coefficient $D_{Ga(III)} = 3.06 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ was used².

TABLE 1—VALUES OF KINETIC PARAMETERS OF Ga^{III} ION REDUCTION IN 6.0 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄ SOLUTION AT VARIABLE TU CONCENTRATION

C_{TU} mol dm ⁻³	$-E_{1/2}$ mV	i_{lim} μA	$E_{1/4} - E_{3/4}$	αn_α	k_{th}^0 cm s ⁻¹ × 10 ⁻³
0	1340	9.2	—	0.30	0.047
1 × 10 ⁻⁴	1320	9.5	0.155	0.33	0.18
1 × 10 ⁻³	1260	10.2	0.136	0.38	0.90
2 × 10 ⁻²	1234	10.0	0.123	0.42	4.40
1 × 10 ⁻¹	1176	10.4	0.115	0.45	6.75
2 × 10 ⁻¹	1140	10.9	0.123	0.42	9.45

The data reveal that the increase of the concentration of TU gives the increase of reversibility of the reduction reaction (increase of αn_α) as well as the acceleration of the electrode process (increase of k_{th}^0).

Influence of TU on Ga^{III} ion reduction in 3.3 mol dm⁻³ NaSCN solution, pH=3.3: Under these conditions one observes two reduction waves. In keeping with the observation of Mac Nevin and Moorhead⁷ the first wave is related to the reduction of gallium–thiocyanate complexes while the other is related to reduction of the products of Ga^{III} ion hydrolysis. Both a logarithmic analysis and the data from Tomeš criterion indicate that the first wave concerns a reversible process, and the other an irreversible one. Gallium–thiourea complexes also arise in the course of Ga^{III} ion reduction in NaSCN solutions at pH=3.3, where one observes a shift of second half-wave potentials towards positive potentials. This is evident both in dc and ac polarograms. Since the first wave is related to reduction of gallium–thiocyanate complexes and the second one to reduction of Ga^{III} ion hydrolysis products, one may conclude that TU eliminates water molecules from the coordination sphere and not thiocyanate ions. Such a conclusion is also supported by the fact that the presence of TU in the solution does not inhibit the catalytic influence of SCN⁻ ions on Ga^{III} ion reduction.

An increase of the pH of the solution probably causes displacement of SCN⁻ ions from gallium–thiocyanate complexes by OH⁻ ions. The increased current of Ga^{III} ion reduction suggests that the influence facilitates the catalytic action of TU on the process under consideration.

It follows from the data that the increase of reversibility and rate of the electrode process with increasing TU concentration in the solution is connected with the formation of gallium–thiourea complexes. As the catalytic action of most substances on electrode processes is related to ligand or active complex adsorption on the electrode surface⁸, it may well be said that in the present

study the forming complex underwent adsorption on mercury.

Ga^{III} ion reduction in the investigated electrolytes takes place in a potential range at which TU adsorbs on mercury via covalent bond between mercury and TU sulphur^{9,10}. On the other hand, TU coordinates metals via one S atom¹¹. Hence, the acceleration of the Ga^{III} ion reduction by TU may be due to the formation of Hg–S–Ga bridge which facilitates charge transfer. A similar mechanism was proposed¹² for the acceleration of Zn^{II} ions reduction on DME by thiourea.

References

1. T. A. KRJUKOVA, S. I. SINJAKOVA and T. W. ARJEFINVA, "Polarography", Moskwa, 1959.
2. E. D. MOORHEAD, *Anal. Chem.*, 1968, 40, 280; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, 72, 3684; *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1968, 18, 197.
3. J. A. I. TURJAN, *Uspechi Chim.*, 1973, 42, 969.
4. A. KUMAR, K. CHANDRA and M. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 133.
5. A. KUMAR, K. CHANDRA and M. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 450.
6. Z. GALUS, "Electroanalytical Methods of Determination Physico-chemical Constants", PWN, Warszawa, 1979, p. 223.
7. W. M. MACNEVIN and E. D. MOORHEAD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 6383.
8. M. TUROWSKA, "The Electrochemistry of Phase Boundaries and Ionogenic Media", PWN, Warszawa, 1984, p. 183.
9. F. E. SCHAPINK, M. QUDEMAN and K. W. LEN, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1960, 56, 415.
10. O. IKEDA, H. GIMBO and H. TAMURA, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1982, 137, 127.
11. H. DWORAHANATH and D. N. SATHYANARAYANA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1978, 47, 706.
12. K. SYKUT, I. SABA, B. MARCZEWSKA and C. DALMATA, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1984, 178, 295.

Conductance Behaviour of Calcium Salts of Fatty Acids in Non-aqueous Medium

K. N. MEHROTRA* and S. K. UPADHYAYA

Department of Chemistry, Agra University, Agra-282 004

Manuscript received 9 June 1987, revised 15 February 1988,
accepted 1 June 1988

THE colloidal and other physicochemical properties of alkali and other metal soaps have already been extensively studied by several workers¹ but the alkaline earth metal soaps have not yet been thoroughly investigated. Recently, the conductance behaviour of the dilute solutions of calcium salts of higher fatty acids in non-aqueous solvents has been investigated^{2,3}. The present paper deals with the conductance behaviour of calcium caproate and valerate in chloroform and propylene glycol mixtures of varying compositions and the results have been used to calculate various parameters, viz. CMC, limiting molecular conductance, dissociation constant and nature of salts, in organic media.

Experimental

Calcium caproate and valerate were prepared by direct metathesis of the corresponding potassium salt with the required amount of aqueous solution of calcium acetate. The soaps were analysed for carbon, hydrogen and metal contents and the results were found in agreement with the theoretically calculated values. The infrared absorption spectra confirmed the absence of free fatty acids in the soaps.

A Toshniwal CL 01.10A digital conductivity meter and a dipping type conductivity cell with platinized electrodes (cell constant, 0.9) were used for measuring conductance of the soap solutions. All the measurements were carried out at $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

Specific conductance, (k): The molar conductance (μ) of the solutions of calcium caproate and valerate involves the effects of both the simple ions and the micelles and so the specific conductance, k , has been plotted against the soap concentration (Fig. 1) to find out the CMC (caproate, $17.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; valerate, $18.2 \times 10^{-3} M$). The value of k of the solutions of calcium soaps in mixtures of varying composition of chloroform and propylene glycol

increases with the increase in the soap concentration but CMC is independent of the solvent composition. The increase in specific conductance with increasing soap concentration may be due to the ionisation of calcium salts into Ca^{2+} and $RCOO^-$ in dilute solutions and due to the formation of micelles at higher soap concentrations. At an appreciable concentration, where the plots of k vs C (soap concentration) show a break, the anions began to aggregate to form ionic micelles. The increase of specific conductance with soap concentration above the CMC may be due to the formation of increasing amounts of ionic micelles of higher conducting power from the simple ions. The results are in agreement with those of rubidium caesium soaps⁴ and potassium laurate⁵. The specific conductance also increases with the increase in propylene glycol concentration in the solvent mixture and this may be due to the high dielectric constant of propylene glycol (32.0 at 20°) as compared to that of chloroform (4.8 at 15°).

Molar conductance (μ) and dissociation constant (K): The molar conductance (μ) decreases with the increase in the soap concentration, and this may be due to the combined effect of ionic atmosphere solvation of ions and decrease of mobility and ionisation with the formation of micelles. The plots of μ vs $C^{1/2}$ (square-root of soap concentration) are not linear, which indicates that calcium soaps behave as weak electrolyte in these solutions. The

Fig. 1. Plots of specific conductance vs concentration: (●) calcium valerate and (○) calcium caproate in 70% chloroform + 30% propylene glycol; (▲) calcium valerate and (△) calcium caproate in 50% chloroform + 50% propylene glycol.

limiting molar conductance (μ_0) cannot be obtained by the usual extrapolation method, and Debye-Hückel-Onsager equation is not applicable to these soap solutions.

Since these soaps in dilute solutions behave as weak electrolytes, an expression for the dissociation of calcium soaps can be developed in Ostwald's manner³. The dissociation constant, K can be expressed as

$$K = \frac{4C^2\alpha^3}{(1-\alpha)} \quad (1)$$

Replacing the degree of dissociation, α , by the conductance ratio, μ/μ_0 and rearranging, one obtains,

$$\mu^2 C^2 = \frac{K\mu_0^3}{4\mu} - \frac{K\mu_0^2}{4} \quad (2)$$

The values of μ_0 and K have been obtained from the slope [$K\mu_0^3/4$] and intercept [$-K\mu_0^2/4$] of the plots of $\mu^2 C^2$ vs $1/\mu$ below the CMC. The values of μ_0 are 7.1 and 5.8 for a solvent mixture containing 50% chloroform and are 1.1 and 1.2 for a mixture of 70% chloroform while the values of K are 2.6×10^{-5} and 2.3×10^{-5} for 50% chloroform and 3.7×10^{-5} and 4.1×10^{-5} for 70% chloroform for calcium caproate and valerate, respectively.

The values of α , calculated by assuming it as equal to the conductance ratio μ/μ_0 and using the value of μ_0 obtained from the plots of $\mu^2 C^2$ vs $1/\mu$ lie between 0.70 and 0.32, which shows that these soaps behave as weak electrolytes in solutions.

References

1. S. S. BHATNAGAR and M. PRASAD, *Kolloid Z.*, 1924, 34, 193; E. ANGELSCU, *Atti Congr. Int. Chim.*, 1938, 2, 77; *Bull. Sec. Sc. Acad. Roum.*, 1940, 22, 251; E. ANGELSCU and A. WOINAROSKY, *Bull. Sec. Acad. Roum.*, 1940, 22, 261; M. E. LAING, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 435; O. R. HOWELL and H. G. B. ROBINSON, *Proc. R. Soc. London, Ser. A*, 1936, 155, 386; A. F. H. WARD, *Proc. R. Soc. London, Ser. A*, 1940, 176, 412; E. C. EVERS and C. A. KRAUS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3049; G. L. BROWN, P. F. GRIEGER and C. A. KRAUS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 95.
2. K. N. MEHROTRA and S. K. UPADHYAYA, *Tenside Detergents*, Communicated; K. N. MEHROTRA and S. K. UPADHYAYA, *Proc. 6th. International Symposium on Surfactants in Solution*.
3. K. N. MEHROTRA and S. K. UPADHYAYA, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 1986, 2, 309.
4. K. N. MEHROTRA, V. K. GODORA and K. K. BOHRA, *Tenside Detergents*, 1983, 20, 196.
5. C. R. BURY and G. A. PARRY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 626.

Thermal Diffusion of Aqueous Magnesium Chloride in an Acid Soil

ANJAN KARMAKAR and S. K. SANYAL*

Department of Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani-741 235

Manuscript received 5 November 1986, revised 23 March 1988, accepted 1 June 1988

THERE have been reports on studies of thermal diffusion of water in soil¹⁻⁴. However, such investigations with aqueous solutions of electro-

lytes have been rather rare. More recently, Sanyal *et al.*⁵⁻⁹ have re-examined the thermodynamic theories of thermal diffusion and pointed out the significance of heat and entropy of transport in characterising the soil-moisture interactions. The present paper gives the results of a study on thermal diffusion of aqueous $MgCl_2$ solution in an acid soil from the district of Jalpaiguri, West Bengal.

The theoretical treatment used is an adaptation of the one based on non-equilibrium thermodynamics and developed by Mukherjee and Sanyal¹⁰ for dealing with diffusion of a solution through an 'open' membrane subjected to a temperature gradient. The expression, giving the heat of transport (\hat{Q}) of a dilute solution across the soil chamber, reads^{9,10}

$$\hat{Q} = RT^2\sigma_1 B_1 - T(\bar{V}_1 + \bar{V}_0) \left(\frac{\Delta P - \Delta\pi}{\Delta T} \right)_{st} \quad (1)$$

where, \bar{V}_1 and \bar{V}_0 are the partial molal volume of the solute and solvent respectively, ΔP and $\Delta\pi$ are the hydrostatic and osmotic pressure differences between the two terminal solution chambers. σ_1 , the 'Soret coefficient' of the solute, is given by the relation,

$$\sigma_1 = -\frac{1}{\bar{m}_1} \left(\frac{\Delta m}{\Delta T} \right)_{st}$$

where, \bar{m}_1 is the mean molal concentration; the thermodynamic factor B_1 is given by

$$B_1 = \left(1 + \frac{\Delta \ln \gamma_1}{\Delta \ln m_1} \right)_{\tau}$$

where, γ_1 is the mean ionic activity coefficient of the solute. Experimentally the term in $\left(\frac{\Delta P - \Delta\pi}{\Delta T} \right)_{st}$

turns out to be negligible for dilute solutions, being at least two orders of magnitude lower than the term in σ_1 , and hence equation (1) approximates to

$$\hat{Q} = RT^2\sigma_1 B_1 \quad (2)$$

\hat{Q} is known to be sensitive to the nature of interactions in the system^{5,10}, and is defined to be the amount of heat absorbed per mole of a diffusing substance from the region it leaves, and released in the region it moves into under isothermal conditions¹¹.

Experimental

The non-isothermal diffusion cell used was similar to the one used by Cary and Taylor^{8,9} and Sanyal *et al.*⁶, and consisted of a three-chamber perspex box in which the soil compartment was sandwiched between, and separated from the two terminal solution chambers (of volume 245.0 cm³ each) by means of two porous ceramic plates. The solution in one compartment was heated by means of a coiled heater connected to a variable voltage supply, while the temperature of the solution in the other terminal chamber was kept lower (which was higher than the ambient temperature) by virtue